

STOP PRESS! A little more Community Project

The Community Project was originally due to end in September however we're delighted to let you know it has been extended to the end of 2024. So there are a few more newsletters in us yet.

The team are currently applying for further funding and will keep you posted on any developments.

Hello and welcome, we have some great stuff for you this month. Read fellow LNL Sharon Coen's top tips for launching a local network and sign up for our very own Replication Games 2024. You'll receive a separate email about the Replication Games - please share this widely. Enjoy!

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Delegates at the University of Salford event

Spotlight on Salford

Our recent [blog](#) spotlights relaunching the University of Salford local network with LNL, [Sharon Coen](#). You can find out how to raise awareness in your department, discover what is happening across your institution, the importance of networking and teamwork, how to fund things when you have no budget, how to structure and run an engaging event and why too many mince pies is not necessarily a bad thing. Read all about the event itself, Sharon's next steps and longer term ambitions [here](#).

Photo credit: Phan Minh Cuong An - Pixabay

Welcomes and goodbyes

There is a steady turnover of LNLs and this section of the newsletter welcomes newcomers and thanks outgoing LNLs. We will try to report all changes but if we miss you, please let us know and we will include you in the next newsletter.

Please welcome:

[Robert Bendall](#), [Samantha Gregory](#), [Eleftheria Rania Kosmidou](#) and [Nilihan Sanal-Hayes](#) are all joining Sharon Coen as co-leads at University of Salford
[Andre Maia Chaga](#) is joining Zoltan Dienes at University of Sussex
[Henry Gonnet](#) and [Dawn Woolley](#) are new LNLs at Leeds Arts University
[Carolyn McNabb](#) is joining Jen Davies at Cardiff University
[Tom Morley](#) is the new LNL at Lancaster University

Huge thanks, goodbye and good luck:

[Candice Morey](#) - Cardiff University
[James Steele](#) - Solent University

We are currently looking for new LNLs within Exeter and Gloucestershire. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

UKRN webinar

[Accelerating the uptake of open research practices: The UKRN Open Research Programme progress and plans](#)

12 September 13:00 - 15:00

This webinar will provide an update on the work of the UKRN Open Research Programme. It will cover the five projects that make up the Programme:

- Training - an extensive train-the-trainer initiative
- Reward and Recognition - the OR4 Project, supporting 49 institutions reforming their recruitment and promotion practices
- Sharing Practice - building and populating a "living website"

- Evaluation Design - including theories of change, a researcher survey and piloting open research indicators
- Sustainability, and Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion

Speakers: Neil Jacobs (UKRN), Tim Newton (King's College London). Others to be confirmed. Register [here](#)

The webinar will be recorded and made available on the UKRN YouTube channel.

Conference

[International Research Culture Conference](#)

University of Warwick 16 September 2024

A showcase of innovative research culture initiatives and the latest research on research culture. Topics covered include researcher career development, open research, improving reproducibility and research integrity. In person spaces are fully booked but you can still register for online viewing. Register [here](#)

INSTITUTE for REPLICATION

Replication Games 2024

Online 5 December 9:00am - 4:30pm

It's here at last – the UKRN Community Project Replication Games 2024 are ready to launch. The info is below. We are also emailing this info - including info about UKRN - to you (it should arrive in your inbox at the same time as this newsletter). Please share this email widely. We are keen to get as many people involved as possible. Dozens would be great, hundreds would be even better. So please sign up, tell your colleagues, friends, family...

The UKRN Community Project are working with the [Institute for Replication \(I4R\)](#) to host online Replication Games on Thursday December 5th, 9:00am - 4:30pm (GMT). Please join us!

What are Replication Games?

Replication Games are free, 1-day events which provide faculty, early career researchers, and graduate students, an opportunity to expand their knowledge of good practices in open science while networking with researchers in a welcoming and fun environment. This is an online event. If several people within the same department are taking part they may wish to work together in a shared space.

Teams of “replicators” will be assigned a published paper which they will work on (1) reproducing and (2) performing sensitivity analyses (robustness checks) from the published paper’s online replication folder. Teams of researchers will then write up a report summarizing the reproducibility and replicability of the published paper.

Completion of a report gives replicators coauthorship on this year’s I4R Meta Paper. If suitable, replicators will then have the opportunity to interact with the original authors which is mediated by I4R.

Benefits of involvement include authorship on a meta-research paper and gaining analytical skills useful both at the individual researcher level and potentially more widely within institutional REF exercises and analyses.

Interested? Sign up here by 12th November 2024:

https://www.surveymonkey.ca/r/I4R_UKRN_Games_2024

About the Institute 4 Replication

I4R is dedicated to advancing credible research through mass reproductions and replications. During 2023, I4R hosted 15 events (Replication Games) around the world, coordinated over 700 researchers, and reproduced or replicated 110 papers. Our discussion papers have been published in academic journals such as: *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, *Economic Inquiry*, *The Economic Journal*. I4R anticipates over 1000 researchers, participating in over 25 events in 2024. Their first meta paper has now been submitted for publication and can be viewed [online](#).

If you have any questions please contact contact@ukrn.org

Other resources

[Digital Humanities Climate Coalition](#)

The speakers at Sharon's Salford event are both involved with the Digital Humanities Climate Coalition toolkit. This is a guide to making your research practices more environmentally responsible. It is geared towards digital practices, but also touches on general areas such as travel and advocacy. They hope it will be relevant to researchers, educators, students, administrators, librarians, technicians, and others. The toolkit aims to highlight actionable solutions, while also critically reflecting on their nuances, in the

broader context of climate justice. It is a community-developed work-in-progress, and you are warmly invited to contribute. Learn more [here](#).

[Open Educational Resources - OER Commons](#)

OER Commons is a public digital library of open educational resources.

LNL Regional Groups

As you know we're keen to establish LNL Regional Groups that can work together at the local/regional level. You should have received emails about this, if not please let us know.

Thanks to those who have already volunteered to lead groups. If you're interested in volunteering please get in touch. A first step could be an in-person or online meeting. There is some Community Project budget to facilitate an in-person meeting, to cover travel costs and catering for a one-day event. Currently this budget ends in December 2024 so any in-person event will need to be in December at the latest.

Reading recommendations

[Principles for Responsible AI Usage in Research](#)

In a rapidly evolving AI landscape Tim-Dorian Knoechel and colleagues describe the principles required for responsible AI usage in research and the development of future policies. Read more [here](#).

[Plurality: the future of collaborative technology and democracy](#)

For a wider look at the use of open data and colloration to drive change, here's a book by E. Glen Weyl, Audrey Tang and colleagues. It's a free online [resource](#). Plurality is a perpetually evolving work that sources content using [gov4git](#), a novel open-source governance technology. This project does not exist without its community and welcomes your input. To learn more, check out the [Plurality repository](#) on GitHub. More information on the project can be found in a recent [interview with Audrey Tang](#).

All this could be yours

Would you like to contribute articles? Get in touch and we'll support you in making it a reality contact@ukrn.org